

UAV-based vineyard water status prediction, univariate and multivariate models or artificial neural networks?

Tomás Poblete^{*1}, Samuel Ortega-Farías¹, Miguel Moreno²

¹ Centro de Investigación y Transferencia en Riego y Agroclimatología (CITRA), Universidad de Talca, Casilla 747, Talca 3460000, Chile.

² Regional Centre of Water Research, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Campus Universitario s/n, 02071, Albacete, España.

Abstract

Background: Stem water potential (Ψ_{stem}) is commonly used to assess water stress (Choné et al., 2001; Williams and Araujo, 2002) and irrigation scheduling (Girona et al., 2006; Jones, 2004). However, the ground-based measurement of Ψ_{stem} provides data with low spatial and temporal resolutions which hinder the spatial variability elucidation (Acevedo-Opazo et al., 2008). Using the remotely sensed multispectral information, it is possible to correlate physiological parameters in a non-invasive way (Baluja et al., 2012; Bellvert et al., 2015; Bellvert et al., 2014; Berni et al., 2009; Li et al., 2016; Rey et al., 2013; Zaman-Allah et al., 2015). However, vegetation indices may not yield reliable Ψ_{stem} with stable performance (Rapaport et al., 2015; Stagakis et al., 2012; Van Beek et al., 2013). This study presents a comparison between different methodologies to predict water status variability using multispectral information obtained from an UAV.

Methods: This study was carried out in a Carménère vineyard located in Talca, Chile. Four treatments and repetitions of regulated deficit irrigation varying from non-stressed to severe stressed were induced. Ψ_{stem} measurements and multispectral information of 530, 550, 570, 670, 700 and 800 nm obtained onboard an UAV were collected in 2014 and 2015. Univariate and multivariate linear models and six artificial neural network (ANN) models were applied to the randomly selected 80% of the collected data and the models were validated against the rest 20% of the data per treatments. Finally R^2 , slope, RMSE, ER were calculated to assess accuracy of the prediction.

Results: The prediction accuracy for both linear models were increased dramatically by ANN models. R^2 , slope, RMSE values for the best linear models were 0.35, 0.05, 0.32 and 0.87, 0.96, 0.12 for the best ANN model. Finally, the best ANN and linear models were applied to the whole aerial images and compared.

Discussion: The best linear model showed lower predictability compared with the best ANN because conventional multispectral indices just detect indirect changes produced by water status. The best ANN model included 550, 570, 670, 700 and 800 nm information, which was consistent with Rapaport et al. (2015).

Conclusion: ANN model (excluding information of 530 nm) was able to predict Ψ_{stem} accurately compared with other ANN and univariate and multivariate linear models.

Background

Water deficit has a negative impact on agriculture and specifically in viticulture where plant cultivation and industry expansion has faced limitations. Also, water deficit may reduce vineyard yield, vegetative growth (Chaves et al., 2007) and grape quality (Chapman et al., 2005). Furthermore, precipitations will decrease between a 20 and 40% in the incoming years (Bates et al., 2008). In that context, it is necessary to adapt technologies and develop new strategies to predict accurately plant water requirements. In this regard, Granier et al. (2006) indicated that measurements of physiological parameters give better information about the whole-plant and intrinsic adaptations to climatic conditions and atmospheric water demands. Among the most studied technologies for monitoring physiological plant responses to water stress highlights sap flow measurement (Escalona et al., 2015, Poblete-Echeverría et al., 2013), dendrometry (Intrigliolo and Castel, 2007), gas exchange (Jara-Rojas et al., 2015, Marino et al., 2014), stomatal conductance (Flexas et al., 2002), canopy temperature (Costa et al., 2013, Deery et al., 2016, Sepúlveda-Reyes et al., 2016, Webber et al., 2016) and plant water potential (Düring and Loveys, 2016, Girona et al., 2006).

This last technique has been a good predictor of vine water status and has been the most commonly used to characterize water stress for vineyards under regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) conditions (Balint and Reynolds, 2017, Choné et al., 2001, Romero et al., 2016). Stem water potential (Ψ_{stem}) is commonly used to assess water stress (Choné et al., 2001, Williams and Araujo, 2002) and irrigation scheduling (Girona et al., 2006, Jones, 2004). Nevertheless due to the ground-based measurement nature of Ψ_{stem} it provides data with low spatial and temporal resolutions which hinder the spatial variability elucidation (Acevedo-Opazo et al., 2008). Using the remotely sensed multispectral information between 500 and 800 nm, it is possible to correlate physiological parameters in a non-invasive way (Baluja et al., 2012, Berni et al., 2009, Rey et al., 2013, Zaman-Allah et al., 2015, Bellvert et al., 2014, Bellvert et al., 2015, Li et al., 2016). However, in vineyards vegetation indices may not yield reliable Ψ_{stem} with stable performance showing a high variation even among cultivars (Van Beek et al., 2013, Stagakis et al., 2012, Rapaport et al., 2015). For example, values of R^2 for the TCARI/OSAVI ranged from 0.58 in Tempranillo (Baluja et al., 2012) to 0.01 in Thompson Seedless (Zarco-Tejada et al., 2013), while those for PRI varied from 0.53 in Thompson Seedless (Zarco-Tejada et al., 2013) to 0.19 in Cabernet Sauvignon (Rapaport et al., 2015). For the NDVI, Baluja et al. (2012) indicated $R^2=0.68$ in Tempranillo while Rapaport et al. (2015) observed $R^2=0.03$ in Cabernet Sauvignon. These differences can be understood because of the non-linear relationship between water status and the mentioned wavelength range. An ANN is inspired in the neural network connection in the human brain where hundreds of billions of interconnected neurons (nodes) process information in parallel. It can be described as a flexible mathematical structure that is capable of identifying complex nonlinear relationships between input and output data sets (Hsu et al., 1995). In this regard, the aim of this study is to compare several vegetation indices, univariate, multivariate models and artificial neural networks and their capability to predict Ψ_{stem} of a drip-irrigated vineyard using a multispectral camera placed on an UAV.

Methods

This study was carried out in a Carménère vineyard located in Talca, Chile. Four treatments and repetitions of regulated deficit irrigation varying from non-stressed to severe stressed were induced. Ψ_{stem} measurements and multispectral information of 530, 550, 570, 670, 700 and 800 nm obtained onboard an UAV were collected in 2014 and 2015. Univariate and multivariate linear models and six artificial neural network (ANN) models were applied to the randomly selected 80% of the collected data. The univariate models were built considering thirteen conventional vegetation indices while multivariate models were built considering the six bands information. The ANN models were built as a MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP) ANN type and a back-propagation process was carried out for weight calculations. The input, hidden and output nodes implement linear, nonlinear and linear functions, respectively (Bishop, 1995). These models were developed using all bands information, and then extracting one band at a time. All the models were validated against the rest 20% of the data per treatments. Finally Pearson coefficient (r) was analyzed in the calibration process and R^2 , slope, RMSE, ER were calculated for validation to assess accuracy of the prediction of the most in the best models.

Results

The correlation for the univariate models ranged an r value between $|0.07|$ and $|0.59|$ where the best correlation was reached with MSR (Table 1.a and 1.b). On the other hand, all the ANN models ranged an r value over 0.75 being all positive. The multivariate models were built selecting an all band model and those bands with higher values of correlation were chosen to develop the models and for being tested in the validation process (Table 1.c).

Table 1.
A. Pearson correlation coefficient for univariate models
B. Pearson correlation coefficient for ANN models
C. Pearson correlation coefficient for single bands

A		B		C	
Index	r	ANN model	r	Band	r
CAR	-0,19	ANN-1	0,9	B1	-0,36
CAR1	0,26	ANN-2	0,92	B2	-0,44
GI	0,27	ANN-3	0,92	B3	-0,32
GNDVI	-0,56	ANN-4	0,88	B4	-0,35
MCARI	-0,15	ANN-5	0,88	B5	-0,36
MCARI1	-0,07	ANN-6	0,82	B6	-0,17
MCARI2	0,22	ANN-7	0,75		
MSAVI	-0,31				
MSR	0,59				
MTVI3	-0,07				
NDVI	-0,45				

Based on Table 1, those conventional vegetation index used for validation were NDVI, MSR and GNDVI (Table 2). All the ANN models were used for validation (Table 3). For multivariate models, all band models and several combinations using B2, B5, B1 and B4 were used (Table 4).

Table 2. Statistical parameters of validation for conventional indices

<i>Validation</i>				
<i>Multispectral indices</i>				
Index	MAE (Mpa)	RMSE (Mpa)	RE (%)	d
NDVI [*]	0,25	0,32	-24,22	0,54
GNDVI ^{**}	0,27	0,34	-25,58	0,51
MSR [*]	0,26	0,33	-24,57	0,53

* p<0.01, **p<0.001

MAE=mean absolute error, RMSE=root mean square error, RE= relative error, d=index of agreement.

Table 3. Statistical parameters of validation for ANN models

<i>ANN models</i>				
Index	MAE (Mpa)	RMSE (Mpa)	RE (%)	d
ANN-1 ^{**}	0,10	0,12	-9,21	0,82
ANN-2 ^{**}	0,10	0,12	-9,11	0,82
ANN-3 ^{**}	0,11	0,13	-9,68	0,80
ANN-4 ^{**}	0,12	0,15	-11,55	0,78
ANN-5 ^{**}	0,13	0,15	-11,61	0,77
ANN-6 ^{**}	0,15	0,20	-15,20	0,73
ANN-7 ^{**}	0,19	0,22	-16,50	0,66

* p<0.01, **p<0.001

MAE=mean absolute error, RMSE=root mean square error, RE= relative error, d=index of agreement.

Table 4. Multivariate models validations

Model	R ²
All-Brands	0,12
B1,B2	0,16
B2,B3	0,15
B2,B4	0,14
B2,B5	0,16
B1,B2,B4	0,14
B2,B4,B5	0,12
B1,B2,B3,B4,B5	0,10

Discussion

Results of conventional indices were consistent with the study carried out by Baluja et al. (2012), who indicated that the higher correlations were observed for NDVI, GNDVI, TCARI/OSAVI and MSR with R² ranging between 0.58 and 0.68. Nevertheless, in our study lower statistical values were found. This can be understood because of the nature of the indices and the reason they were developed. These indices have the use of NIR information in common in their calculation. NIR has a high reflectance on plant tissue (Major et al., 1990) in contrast to the RED wavelength used for NDVI, MSR and TCARI-OSAVI, which has a high absorbance by Chl (Pu and Gong, 2000). Despite the inclusion of these wavelengths, these indices can only indirectly detect water status differences, because they were developed to represent different physiological variables that change according to different levels of water status. In this context, NDVI has been reported as a good indicator of 'vegetative expression' (Acevedo-Opazo et al., 2008) while GNDVI has been reported as a better form to detect Chl pigment concentration, (Gitelson and Merzlyak, 1998), which is modified under stress conditions. MSR was developed to improve the relationship of other indices with biophysical parameters in boreal forests (Chen, 1996). This variation could be associated with the non-linear effect between water stress on different wavelength reflectance. The relationship between spectral indices and Ψ_{stem} is due to indirect changes produced by different levels of water stress, in contrast to thermal information where direct effects such as stomatal closure can be assessed by thermal changes (Bellvert et al., 2014, Bellvert et al., 2015, Santesteban et al., 2017). In this context, we suggested that these indirect changes can be assessed by non-linear relationships using information between 500 and 800 nm. For the ANN-2 model, that excluded R530 is consistent with Rapaport et al. (2015), who found that at 530 nm the relation with water status increase. Since our study was carried out between two different seasons and in different months, we suggest that R670 and R800 wavelengths are relevant to represent all plant physiology differences presented in the field caused by the treatments because these wavelengths can detect plant tissue and have low and high reflectance in bushy (healthy) plants, respectively (Ollinger, 2011; Wang et al., 2007). Finally, the ANN-2 model was applied to a whole flight with the aim of predict the Ψ_{stem} for the vineyard (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Ψ_{stem} prediction for a whole flight in a Carménère vineyard

Conclusion

High resolution multispectral images were obtained from an UAV platform allowed the prediction of the stem water potential spatial variability in a Mediterranean Carménère vineyard located in Talca, Maule Region, Chile. Multispectral indices models showed low predictability with Ψ_{stem} and multivariate models were not able of predicting stem water potential. Nevertheless artificial neural network models improved highly the Ψ_{stem} prediction compared with both linear models.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by the Chilean government through the projects CONICYT-PFCHA (No 2014- 21140229) and FONDECYT (No 1160997) and by the Universidad de Talca through the research program Adaptation of Agriculture to Climate Change (A2C2).

References

- Acevedo-Opazo C, Tisseyre B, Guillaume S, Ojeda H 2008. The potential of high spatial resolution information to define within-vineyard zones related to vine water status. *Precision Agriculture* 9: 285–302.
- Balint G, & Reynolds AG 2017. Irrigation level and time of imposition impact vine physiology, yield components, fruit composition and wine quality of Ontario Chardonnay. *Scientia Horticulturae* 214: 252–272.
- Baluja J, Diago MP, Balda P, Zorer R, Meggio F, Morales F, Tardaguila J 2012. Assessment of vineyard water status variability by thermal and multispectral imagery using an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). *Irrigation Science* 30: 511–522.
- Bates B, Kundzewicz ZW, Wu S, Palutikof J 2008. Climate change and water: technical paper vi, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
- Bellvert J, Marsal J, Girona J, Zarco-Tejada PJ 2015. Seasonal evolution of crop water stress index in grapevine varieties determined with high-resolution remote sensing thermal imagery. *Irrigation Science* 33: 81–93.
- Bellvert J, Zarco-Tejada PJ, Girona J, Fereres E 2014. Mapping crop water stress index in a 'Pinot-noir' vineyard: comparing ground measurements with thermal remote sensing imagery from an unmanned aerial vehicle. *Precision agriculture* 15: 361–376.
- Berni JA, Zarco-Tejada PJ, Suárez L, Fereres E 2009. Thermal and narrowband multispectral remote sensing for vegetation monitoring from an unmanned aerial vehicle. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 47: 722–738.
- Costa JM, Grant OM, Chaves MM 2013. Thermography to explore plant–environment interactions. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 64: 3937–3949.
- Chapman DM, Roby G, Ebeler SE, Guinard JX, Matthews MA 2005. Sensory attributes of Cabernet Sauvignon wines made from vines with different water status. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research* 11: 339–347.
- Chaves MM, Santos TP, Souza CRD, Ortuño M, Rodrigues M, Lopes C, Maroco J, Pereira JS 2007. Deficit irrigation in grapevine improves water-use efficiency while controlling vigour and production quality. *Annals of Applied Biology* 150: 237–252.
- Chen JM 1996. Evaluation of vegetation indices and a modified simple ratio for boreal applications. *Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing* 22: 229–242.
- Choné X, Van Leeuwen C, Dubourdieu D, Gaudillière JP 2001. Stem water potential is a sensitive indicator of grapevine water status. *Annals of botany* 87: 477–483.
- Deery DM, Rebetzke GJ, Jimenez-Berni JA, James RA, Condon AG, Bovill WD, Hutchinson P, Scarrow J, Davy R, Furbank RT 2016. Methodology for high-throughput field phenotyping of canopy temperature using airborne thermography. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 7 p.
- Düring H, Loveys B 2016. Diurnal changes in water relations and abscisic acid in field grown *Vitis vinifera* cvs. I. Leaf water potential components and leaf conductance under humid temperate and semiarid conditions. *VITIS-Journal of Grapevine Research* 21: 223.
- zenodo.org/communities/pa17

- Escalona J, Flexas J, Medrano H 2015. Drought effects on water flow, photosynthesis and growth of potted grapevines. *VITIS-Journal of Grapevine Research* 41: 57.
- Girona J, Mata M, Del Campo J, Arbonés A, Bartra E, Marsal J 2006. The use of midday leaf water potential for scheduling deficit irrigation in vineyards. *Irrigation Science* 24: 115–127.
- Gitelson AA, Merzlyak MN 1998. Remote sensing of chlorophyll concentration in higher plant leaves. *Advances in Space Research* 22: 689–692.
- Granier C, Aguirrezabal L, Chenu K, Cookson SJ, Dauzat M, Hamard P, Thioux JJ, Rolland G, Bouchier-Combaud S, Lebaudy A 2006. PHENOPSIS, an automated platform for reproducible phenotyping of plant responses to soil water deficit in *Arabidopsis thaliana* permitted the identification of an accession with low sensitivity to soil water deficit. *New Phytologist* 169: 623–635.
- Hsu KL, Gupta HV, Sorooshian S 1995. Artificial neural network modeling of the rainfall-runoff process. *Water resources research* 31: 2517–2530.
- Intrigliolo D, Castel J 2007. Evaluation of grapevine water status from trunk diameter variations. *Irrigation Science* 26: 49–59.
- Jara-Rojas F, Ortega-Farías S, Valdés-Gómez H, Acevedo-Opazo C 2015. Gas exchange relations of ungrafted grapevines (cv. Carménère) growing under irrigated field conditions. *South African Journal of Enology and Viticulture* 36: 231–242.
- Jones HG 2004. Irrigation scheduling: advantages and pitfalls of plant-based methods. *Journal of experimental botany* 55: 2427–2436.
- Li T, Hao X, Kang S 2016. Spatial variability of grape yield and its association with soil water depletion within a vineyard of arid northwest China. *Agricultural Water Management*.
- Major D, Baret F, Guyot G 1990. A ratio vegetation index adjusted for soil brightness. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 11: 727–740.
- Marino G, Pallozzi E, Coccozza C, Tognetti R, Giovannelli A, Cantini C, Centritto M 2014. Assessing gas exchange, sap flow and water relations using tree canopy spectral reflectance indices in irrigated and rainfed *Olea europaea* L. *Environmental and Experimental Botany* 99: 43–52.
- Poblete-Echeverría C, Samuel Ortega 2013. Evaluation of single and dual crop coefficients over a drip-irrigated Merlot vineyard (*Vitis vinifera* L.) using combined measurements of sap flow sensors and an eddy covariance system. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research* 19: 249–260.
- Pu R-L, Gong P 2000. *Hyperspectral remote sensing and its applications*. Higher Education, Beijing. 8 p.
- Rapaport T, Hochberg U, Shoshany M, Karnieli A, Rachmilevitch S 2015. Combining leaf physiology, hyperspectral imaging and partial least squares-regression (PLS-R) for grapevine water status assessment. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 109: 88–97.
- Rey C, Martin M, Lobo A, Luna I, Diago MP, Millan B, Tardáguila J 2013. Multispectral imagery acquired from a UAV to assess the spatial variability of a Tempranillo vineyard. *Precision agriculture'13*.
- Romero P, García JG, Fernández-Fernández JI, Muñoz RG, Del Amor Saavedra F, Martínez-Cutillas A 2016. Improving berry and wine quality attributes and vineyard economic efficiency by long-term deficit irrigation practices under semiarid conditions. *Scientia Horticulturae* 203: 69–85.
- Santesteban L, Di Gennaro S, Herrero-Langreo A, Miranda C, Royo J, Matese A 2017. High-resolution UAV-based thermal imaging to estimate the instantaneous and seasonal variability of plant water status within a vineyard. *Agricultural Water Management* 183: 49–59.
- Sepúlveda-Reyes D, Ingram B, Bardeen M, Zúñiga M, Ortega-Farías S, Poblete-Echeverría C 2016. Selecting Canopy Zones and Thresholding Approaches to Assess Grapevine Water Status by Using Aerial and Ground-Based Thermal Imaging. *Remote Sensing* 8: 822.
- Stagakis S, González-Dugo V, Cid P, Guillén-Climent ML, Zarco-Tejada PJ 2012. Monitoring water stress and fruit quality in an orange orchard under regulated deficit irrigation using narrow-band structural and physiological remote sensing indices. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 71: 47–61.

Van Beek J, Tits L, Somers B, Coppin P 2013. Stem water potential monitoring in pear orchards through WorldView-2 multispectral imagery. *Remote Sensing* 5: 6647–6666.

Webber H, Ewert F, Kimball B, Siebert S, White J, Wall G, Ottman MJ, Trawally D, Gaiser T 2016. Simulating canopy temperature for modelling heat stress in cereals. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 77: 143–155.

Williams L, Arajio F 2002. Correlations among predawn leaf, midday leaf, and midday stem water potential and their correlations with other measures of soil and plant water status in *Vitis vinifera*. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* 127: 448–454.

Zaman-Allah M, Vergara O, Arous J, Tarekegne A, Magorokosho C, Zarco-Tejada P, Hornero A, Albà AH, Das B, Craufurd P 2015. Unmanned aerial platform-based multi-spectral imaging for field phenotyping of maize. *Plant methods* 11: 1.

Zarco-Tejada PJ, González-Dugo V, Williams L, Suárez L, Berni JA, Goldhamer D, Fereres E 2013. A PRI-based water stress index combining structural and chlorophyll effects: Assessment using diurnal narrow-band airborne imagery and the CWSI thermal index. *Remote sensing of environment* 138: 38–50.